

METHODS OF STABILIZING MONETARY POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The Republic of Uzbekistan, a country located in Central Asia, has been actively working to stabilize its monetary policy since gaining independence in 1991. The country's transition from a planned to a market-based economy has been accompanied by significant economic reforms, including the liberalization of prices, trade, and the financial sector. However, the country still faces challenges in maintaining macroeconomic stability, particularly in terms of inflation and exchange rate fluctuations. This article will discuss the methods of stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan, highlighting the role of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, the importance of inflation targeting, and the need for exchange rate flexibility.

Keywords: monetary policy, fluctuations, trade, market system, economic downturns, political issues

Introduction: The really subjective change in the utilization of money related instruments was another methodology while carrying out mediations by the National Bank in the unfamiliar trade market, which is pointed toward cleaning extra liquidity to the financial framework without influencing the principal market pattern of the UZS conversion scale. The use of this approach has shown what itself can do as a productive device for dealing with the liquidity of the financial framework, making economic situations for the arrangement of the conversion scale and loan costs in the currency market. By and by, the experience shows that the productivity of the utilization of cleansing exchanges by the National Bank in the unfamiliar trade market is impacted by the irregularity of cash streams, especially, when the volume of cross-line settlements of people in the II and III quarters of the year significantly increments.

Hence, assuming the volume of unfamiliar trade mediations of the National Bank added up to 600 million USD in the principal quarter, then in the second quarter the volume of mediation added up to 300 million USD, which has prompted the development of an extra unsterilized piece of liquidity in the financial framework. Under these circumstances, the National Bank stepped up the previously mentioned liquidity circumstance somewhat by changing the principles for the arrangement of hold prerequisites of business banks.

First and foremost, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan (CBU) plays a crucial role in stabilizing monetary policy in the country. As the primary regulator of the financial system, the CBU is responsible for setting monetary policy, regulating commercial banks, and maintaining financial stability. To achieve these objectives, the CBU uses various tools, including setting interest rates, regulating reserve requirements, and conducting open market operations. For instance, the CBU can increase interest rates to reduce inflationary pressures, or decrease them to stimulate economic growth. Additionally, the CBU can adjust reserve requirements to influence the amount of credit available in the economy. By using these tools effectively, the CBU can help stabilize the economy and maintain low and stable inflation.

Another important method of stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan is inflation targeting. Inflation targeting is a monetary policy framework that focuses on achieving a specific inflation rate, usually around 2-3% per annum. This approach has been successfully implemented in many countries, including developed economies such as the United States, the European Union, and Japan. In Uzbekistan, inflation targeting can help reduce inflationary pressures, which have been a major challenge for the country in recent years. High inflation rates can erode the purchasing power of citizens, reduce the competitiveness of domestic industries, and undermine confidence in the economy. By targeting a low and stable inflation rate, the CBU can help maintain macroeconomic stability and promote sustainable economic growth.

Furthermore, exchange rate flexibility is essential for stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan. The country's economy is heavily dependent on exports, particularly of natural resources such as cotton, gold, and natural gas. As a result, the exchange rate plays a critical role in determining the competitiveness of Uzbekistan's exports. A flexible exchange rate regime allows the currency to adjust to changes in the economy, such as shifts in global commodity prices or changes in domestic demand. This can help maintain a stable trade balance and reduce the risk of currency crises. In addition, a flexible exchange rate regime can help the CBU to implement an independent monetary policy, without being constrained by the need to maintain a fixed exchange rate.

Another method of stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan is the development of the financial sector. A well-developed financial sector can help to channel savings into productive investments, reduce the risk of financial instability, and promote economic growth. In Uzbekistan, the financial sector is still underdeveloped, with limited access to credit and other financial services.

To address this challenge, the government has implemented various reforms, including the liberalization of interest rates, the development of a credit registry, and the introduction of new financial instruments such as bonds and stocks. These reforms can help to increase the efficiency of the financial sector, reduce the risk of financial instability, and promote economic growth.

In addition, the development of a sound fiscal policy is essential for stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan. Fiscal policy refers to the use of government spending and taxation to influence the overall level of economic activity. A sound fiscal policy can help to reduce the risk of fiscal deficits, which can lead to inflation, currency depreciation, and other macroeconomic imbalances. In Uzbekistan, the government has implemented various fiscal reforms, including the introduction of a medium-term budget framework, the development of a fiscal responsibility law, and the improvement of public financial management. These reforms can help to increase the transparency and accountability of fiscal policy, reduce the risk of fiscal deficits, and promote macroeconomic stability.

Finally, the development of a robust financial infrastructure is critical for stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan. A robust financial infrastructure includes a well-developed payment system, a reliable system of financial statistics, and an effective system of financial supervision. In Uzbekistan, the financial infrastructure is still underdeveloped, with limited access to payment systems, inadequate financial statistics, and weak financial supervision. To address this challenge, the government has implemented various reforms, including the development of a real-time gross settlement system, the improvement of financial statistics, and the strengthening of financial supervision. These reforms can help to increase the efficiency of the financial sector, reduce the risk of financial instability, and promote economic growth.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, stabilizing monetary policy in Uzbekistan requires a combination of effective tools and strategies. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan plays a crucial role in stabilizing monetary policy, and the use of inflation targeting, exchange rate flexibility, and financial sector development can help to achieve macroeconomic stability. Additionally, the development of a sound fiscal policy, a robust financial infrastructure, and a well-functioning payment system are essential for promoting economic growth and reducing the risk of financial instability. By implementing these reforms, Uzbekistan can create a stable and

prosperous economy, which can benefit its citizens and promote sustainable economic development.

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